

TITLE

Systematic Review Protocol: The effect of injection therapies on surgery rates in persons with radicular pain from a herniated lumbar disc.

AUTHORS

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BACKGROUND

Radicular pain caused by a herniated lumbar disc may resolve naturally, yet persistent pain often necessitates treatment beyond first-line options such as bed rest, medication, and physical therapy. In certain regions, such as the US, epidural steroid injections—including transforaminal steroid injections (TFSIs)—are often used as a less invasive alternative to surgery to reduce nerve root inflammation. Their application is more variable in Europe and discouraged in Denmark due to limited evidence (Stochkendahl et al., 2018).

Given the generally favourable prognosis for lumbar disc herniations and emerging evidence of short-term benefits (Manchikanti et al., 2015), TFSIs are often employed as part of a sequential treatment strategy to manage persistent radicular pain, deferring surgery, which is used only when TFSI effects are insufficient. This systematic review aims to expand and update existing reviews (Bhatti & Kim, 2016; Smith et al., 2020) on surgical avoidance in patients receiving TFSIs or similar interventions.

REVIEW QUESTION

What is the effect of image-guided, percutaneous injection therapies on surgery rate (primary outcome), as well as physical functioning, pain level, health-related quality of life and adverse events caused by injection (secondary outcomes) in persons with radicular pain from a herniated lumbar disc?

PICO

Population:

Adults with lumbar herniated disc and radiating pain in the legs. MRI and clinical findings are convincingly related.

The study population may include persons with neuropathic leg pain, as long as they have lumbar disc herniation.

Intervention(s):

Interventions are image-guided, percutaneous injection therapies performed with the needle tip placed outside the central vertebral foramen. Articles are not filtered on type of needle, type of imaging or injectate. Injectates are considered active treatments when defined as such by the authors, for example steroid + anaesthetic or steroid alone.

Comparator(s):

Comparators in included studies may receive a placebo injection or usual (non-invasive, conservative) care without injection therapy.

In addition, we include relevant treatment groups from studies where they are compared to non-relevant groups (non-relevant groups may be participants with radiculopathy not due to a herniated disc or receiving injection through an excluded injection method).

Outcomes:

Primary outcome: Proportion of participants eventually having surgery. When available, we also record the time from injection to surgery, as well as any other health care used due to an insufficient effect of the injection.

Secondary outcomes: Pain level (radicular pain in legs) reported using the Visual Analogue Score, VAS (Wewers & Lowe, 1990), or the Numeric Rating Scale, NRS (Farrar et al., 2001), and functioning reported using the Oswestry Disability Score, ODI (Fairbank & Pynsent, 2000), or Roland-Morris Disability Questionnaire, RMDQ (Roland & Morris, 1983). We will also include pain and functioning scores reported using the MOS 36-Item Short-Form Health Survey, SF-36 (Ware & Sherbourne, 1992), health-related quality of life, EQ-5D (The EuroQoL Group, 1990), as well as adverse events caused by the injections.

METHODS

Eligibility criteria

This systematic review will include full-text publications reporting results from randomised controlled trials and observational studies (cohort and case/control studies). We exclude technical notes, review papers, meta-analyses, case reports, expert opinions, economic analyses, and publications with incomplete information in databases. If results are reported in a format that is unsuitable for analysis, we will contact the authors to request results in a format that enables inclusion.

The included study populations comprise persons with radicular pain due to (a) herniated lumbar disc(s). Study populations are ineligible if they include persons with radicular pain in the legs due to spinal stenosis, "failed back surgery syndrome"/"post-surgery syndrome", disc cysts or facet joint pain.

Eligible injections are referred to as selective nerve root block and foraminal, extraforaminal, transforaminal, perineural, and periradicular injections. Ineligible injections are epidural injections (i.e., the needle tip was placed in the central vertebral foramen), interlaminar injection, medial branch blocks, facet injection, intra-articular facet injection, intra-discal injection and muscular infiltration.

Articles reporting on epidural injections (i.e. the needle tip was placed in the central vertebral foramen) are not relevant to this review. However, some authors use the term "epidural" to describe injections outside the central vertebral foramen. Therefore, we include articles containing the term "epidural" in the title/abstract screening and assess the injection description in detail during the full-text review.

We will not search for specific injectates and accept all steroids and anaesthetics. Platelet-rich plasma and ozone are ineligible injectates. We exclude studies with combined medical interventions, such as steroid injections and gabapentin.

Information Sources

We will search five bibliographic databases for published and accepted articles: Medline (Ovid), Embase (Ovid), Scopus (Elsevier), Web of Science (Clarivate), and the Cochrane Central Registry of Controlled Trials (John Wiley & Sons). In addition, we search for relevant ongoing studies and clinical study reports in three trial registries: ClinicalTrials.gov, the WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP), and the MRC Clinical Trials Unit.

When eligible studies have been included, they are used in a forward search based on the Scopus citation index (Lefebvre et al., 2024). The list of cited literature from existing reviews in this research area is screened according to the procedures also used for articles from bibliographic databases. to identify relevant original studies. Our citation searches will be documented when reporting the results from the review.

Search strategies

Search strategies were peer-reviewed by an information specialist according to the PRESS Evidence-Based Checklist (McGowan et al., 2016). A series of pilot searches qualified the strategies, using known relevant articles as indicators. Searches will span the entire period from the inception of each bibliographic database (MEDLINE(R) ALL from 1946; Embase Classic + Embase from 1947; Web of Science Core Collection from 1900) until the date of the search. In Appendix 1, the search strategies for all databases are presented. The searches will be reported according to the PRISMA for Searching (PRISMA-S) checklist (Rethlefsen et al., 2020), included as Appendix 2.

All articles retrieved from literature database searches are exported to EndNote™ (The EndNote Team, 2013), merged, and duplicates are removed. The resulting articles are exported to Covidence (Veritas Health Innovation, 2024), where additional duplicates will be removed before screening.

Screening process

Two independent reviewers will screen titles and abstracts using Covidence (HJ is the first reviewer, while SO and AA share the second reviewer tasks). Any conflicts will be solved by consensus. A PRISMA 2020 flow diagram is set up to present the screening process. At this stage, we screen based on population and intervention only (please see the section on Publication Bias below). All articles that may be eligible will proceed to full-text review by HJ and SO. HJ will enter citation and contact details for all articles undergoing full-text review, and HJ and SO will record the decisions from the full-text review in separate copies of the table in Appendix 3. Articles may be excluded due to 1) an ineligible study population, 2) an ineligible intervention or 3) ineligible outcomes or data format. Study characteristics are recorded by HJ for all included articles.

We include articles reporting original results published in English, German or one of the Scandinavian languages.

Data extraction

Two reviewers (HJ and SO) will be involved in the data extraction process. HJ will manually extract the data and enter it into Microsoft Excel, while SO will verify the accuracy of the data. Any inconsistencies will be solved by consensus. Initially, we will extract all relevant outcome data to get an overview of available data in the included articles. The primary outcome, surgery rate, may be reported as a main outcome of the study or as a supplementary finding mentioned in the results or discussion section of an article. Data will be collected in the table in Appendix 4.

A core set of data is recorded for all studies, including the type of intervention, herniations included in each study, duration of symptoms, age and sex ratio of the study population, injectate and number of injections allowed in each study. This table has been pilot-tested by HJ and SO, who independently typed in data for three articles and reached a joint decision on how to add new types of outcomes/follow-up time points to the template. HJ and SO also reached a consensus on procedures for handling differences in data format among articles; all relevant data will be added to the template to provide an overview for assessment of ultimately available data suitable for aggregation and analysis.

Risk-of-Bias Assessment

The risk of bias for each study is assessed by HJ and SO independently using the Quality Assessment Tool for Quantitative Studies developed by the Effective Public Health Practice Project (EPHPP) (Thomas et al., 2004). The EPHPP tool can be applied to both randomised and observational studies, and potential bias is assessed across six categories of study characteristics: selection of the study population, study design, confounders, incomplete blinding of assessors and participants, data collection methods, and withdrawals and dropouts. HJ and SO pilot the tool on three articles, and any assessment conflicts will be solved by consensus. Results from the risk-of-bias assessment are reported using the online robvis visualisation tool.

Data synthesis

A meta-analysis of the primary outcome will be performed if the extracted data permit. If extracted data permit, in a subgroup analysis, we will compare results for patients with a short (<3 months) versus a long (≥3 months) duration from symptom onset to injection. Otherwise, we will provide a narrative presentation of the findings from the included articles.

Publication bias

To mitigate the risk of bias due to selective non-reporting or under-reporting, we conduct searches in project databases for data that has not yet been published.

If we identify otherwise eligible articles in the full-text review that do not report on the surgery rate, we will contact the authors to request unpublished data on the surgery rate in the study population(s). The proportion of these articles will be taken into account when discussing the overall results of the review.

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TIMELINE

January – December 2026

PERSPECTIVES

We aim to assess the evidence regarding the impact of injection therapies on surgical rates in individuals with radicular pain caused by a herniated lumbar disc. The findings will be discussed in the context of standardising clinical practice and implementing a stepped care approach to the management of radicular pain.

CITED LITERATURE

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APPENDIX 1 – Search strategies

APPENDIX 2 – PRISMA-S checklist

APPENDIX 3 – Decisions from full-text reviews

APPENDIX 4 - Data collection table